

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

Proposal No.: 848261

Deliverable D7.3: Report on Status of Posting Results

Deliverable No. D21 – WP7

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1 Introduction

This deliverable aims to report about the successful public posting of the results of the UNITI randomized clinical trial.

2 UNITI-RCT

The main aim of the UNITI-RCT was to compare single and combination therapies for the treatment of tinnitus. Therefore, a multicenter, parallel-arm, randomized controlled clinical trial was conducted with patients randomly assigned to ten treatment arms of single and combination treatment. Treatment was conducted for 12 weeks. Cognitive-behavioral therapy, hearing aids, structured counseling and sound therapy were administered either alone or as a combination of two treatments resulting in 10 treatment arms.

A placebo group was not included in this trial, as the answer to the main research question, which is the comparison of single and combined treatment, did not require a placebo arm. As shown in deliverable D6.2, there is a statistically significant difference between the treatment arms with combinational treatment compared to the treatment arms with single treatment. In short: combinational treatments showed an advantage over single treatments. Furthermore, the main objective of the UNITI project was to develop a decision support system (DSS) for chronic tinnitus patients and the data collected in the UNITI RCT was the basis for the development of the DSS. Data from a placebo group would not have been useful for the development of the DSS. The UNITI project was funded as a Research and Innovation Action with the main purpose of developing new innovations (in this case a decision support system), therefore we aimed to use the limited budget of the project to reach this goal - and at the same time avoid costs that are not necessarily needed for the DSS development. Thus, it was decided not to include a placebo group. This decision was already taken while writing the proposal. It remains a speculation if the project would have been funded if we had taken a different decision.

For the primary contrast of single versus combination treatment, it was estimated that, with a two-tailed alpha level of less than 0.05, the given sample size of $N = 461$ provides the RCT with 90% power to detect an effect size of 0.30.

The study was closed on the 19. of December 2022. Only data from patients who finished their treatment phase up to this date, were included in the analysis of the RCT. However, at some

clinical sites, the teams decided to keep going with the UNITI treatments, that seemed to be helpful for the patients. The number of tinnitus patients in Europe is continuously increasing and the number of tinnitus experts offering treatment for them is limited. Since the clinical routine was already established and some of the treatments (e.g. the treatment with the UNITI app) are of low costs, it was possible to help some more tinnitus patients, even after December 19, 2022. The data of these additional patients did not enter the analysis of the RCT (as mentioned above, the data collection of the official UNITI study was closed on December 19, 2022), however, the data of these patients will not be thrown away. Instead, the data will be collected for other analyses that might happen after the end of the UNITI project. The database (tinnitus-database.eu) is open for this additional data with the same data scheme, but marked as data that does not belong to the UNITI RCT.

The results of the randomized clinical trial (RCT) with 461 included patients are reported in deliverable D6.2. The manuscript reporting on the RCT results is already prepared and currently in internal review by the UNITI consortium. It will be submitted to a high impact peer-reviewed journal. Once a preprint is available, the respective section in clinical trial.gov will be updated.

3 Search Results ClinicalTrials.gov

The screenshot shows the ClinicalTrials.gov interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the NIH logo and 'National Library of Medicine' text. Below this, the 'ClinicalTrials.gov' logo is visible on the left, and navigation links like 'About This Site', 'Find Studies', 'Data About Studies', 'Study Basics', and 'PRS Info' are on the right. A dark blue bar indicates 'Record 1 of 1' and a 'Return to Search' link. Below this, a breadcrumb trail shows 'Home > Search Results > Study Record'. A prominent yellow warning box contains the text: 'The U.S. government does not review or approve the safety and science of all studies listed on this website. Read our full disclaimer for details.' Below the warning, the study status is 'COMPLETED'. The study title is 'Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients - Randomized Clinical Trial (UNITI-RCT) (UNITI-RCT)'. Additional details include: ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT04663828; Sponsor: UNITI Consortium; Information provided by: UNITI Consortium (Responsible Party); Last Update Posted: 2023-08-14.

Figure 1 Study Record ClinicalTrials.gov

Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients - Randomized Clinical Trial (UNITI-RCT) (UNITI-RCT)

ClinicalTrials.gov ID NCT04663828

Sponsor **UNITI** Consortium

Information provided by **UNITI** Consortium (Responsible Party)

Last Update Posted 2023-08-14

Study Details | **Table View** | No Results Posted | Record History

On this page

- Trial Contacts
- Study Record Dates
- Outcome Measures
- Trial Description
- Recruitment Information
- Administrative Information

Trial Contacts

Contacts ICMJE Contact information is only displayed when the study is recruiting subjects

Study Record Dates

First Submitted	ICMJE	2020-12-04
First Posted	ICMJE	2020-12-11
Last Update Posted		2023-08-14
Last Verified		2023-08

Outcome Measures

Change History [See all versions of this study](#)

Figure 2 Table View clinicalTrials.gov

The manuscript of the RCT-paper that describes the clinical results of the RCT is in preparation As soon as the paper is available as a pre-print), the related section in clinical trial.gov will be updated (Figure 3 Study Results)

Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients - Randomized Clinical Trial (UNITI-RCT) (UNITI-RCT)

ClinicalTrials.gov ID [NCT04663828](#)

Sponsor [UNITI Consortium](#)

Information provided by [UNITI Consortium \(Responsible Party\)](#)

Last Update Posted [2023-08-14](#)

Study record dates +

Study Details
Table View
No Results Posted
Record History

On this page

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Results Overview

No Study Results Posted on ClinicalTrials.gov for this Study

Study results have not been submitted. This may be because the study isn't done, the deadline for submitting results has not passed, or this study isn't required to submit results.

Recruitment Status	Actual Primary Completion Date	Actual Study Completion Date
Completed	2022-12-19	2023-06-15

Figure 3 Study Results clinicalTrials.gov

Study Details
Table View
No Results Posted
Record History

Study Record Versions

- This table shows the list of all the versions of this study record arranged in order by date.
- The first column shows the date the study record was updated, and the second column shows the elements in the study record that were changed.
 - To view a version of a study record, click the version date.
 - To compare versions, select two versions using the check boxes and click the "Compare" button at the bottom of the list.

	Date	Changes
<input type="checkbox"/>	2020-12-10	None (earliest version on record)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2021-08-25	Recruitment Status Study Status Contacts/Locations
<input type="checkbox"/>	2022-12-01	Study Status Contacts/Locations References
<input type="checkbox"/>	2023-08-10	Recruitment Status Study Status Study Design References

Compare

Figure 4 Record History clinicalTrials.gov

4 General Publications

The statistical analysis plan and the study protocol have already been published and are listed under general publications in the study section of clinicalTrials

Publications

The person responsible for entering information about the study voluntarily provides these publications. These may be about anything related to the study.

GENERAL PUBLICATIONS

- [Schoisswohl S, Langguth B, Schecklmann M, Bernal-Robledano A, Boecking B, Cederroth CR, Chalanouli D, Cima R, Denys S, Dettling-Papargyris J, Escalera-Balsera A, Espinosa-Sanchez JM, Gallego-Martinez A, Giannopoulou E, Hidalgo-Lopez L, Hummel M, Kikidis D, Koller M, Lopez-Escamez JA, Marcrum SC, Markatos N, Martin-Lagos J, Martinez-Martinez M, Martinez-Martinez M, Ferron MM, Mazurek B, Mueller-Locatelli N, Neff P, Oppel K, Perez-Carpena P, Robles-Bolivar P, Rose M, Schiele T, Schiller A, Simoes J, Stark S, Staudinger S, Stege A, Verhaert N, Schlee W. Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients \(UNITI\): a study protocol for a multi-center randomized clinical trial. *Trials*. 2021 Dec 4;22\(1\):875. doi: 10.1186/s13063-021-05835-z. \[↗\]\(#\)](#)
- [Simoes JP, Schoisswohl S, Schlee W, Basso L, Bernal-Robledano A, Boecking B, Cima R, Denys S, Engelke M, Escalera-Balsera A, Gallego-Martinez A, Gallus S, Kikidis D, Lopez-Escamez JA, Marcrum SC, Markatos N, Martin-Lagos J, Martinez-Martinez M, Mazurek B, Vassou E, Jarach CM, Mueller-Locatelli N, Neff P, Niemann U, Omar HK, Puga C, Schleicher M, Unnikrishnan V, Perez-Carpena P, Pryss R, Robles-Bolivar P, Rose M, Schecklmann M, Schiele T, Schobel J, Spiliopoulou M, Stark S, Vogel C, Wunder N, Zachou Z, Langguth B. The statistical analysis plan for the unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients randomized clinical trial \(UNITI-RCT\). *Trials*. 2023 Jul 24;24\(1\):472. doi: 10.1186/s13063-023-07303-2. \[↗\]\(#\)](#)

* Find [Publications about Study Results](#) and related [Pubmed Publications](#) in the "Results" section of the study record.

Figure 5 General publications clinicalTrials.gov

5 Publications Related to the UNITI-Project

A list of all publications related to the UNITI project can be found on the UNITI website under the menu item scientific publications.

Link: <https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net/index.php/research/scientific-publications>

The project started in January 2020.

Listed in the below table, you will find all scientific publications by the UNITI consortium published during the entire project duration.

2020 - 2023

Journal publications

	Puga, C., Niemann, U., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2023). A cost-based multi-layer network approach for the discovery of patient phenotypes. <i>International Journal of Data Science and Analytics</i> , 1-21. https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.09032
paper available for download	Simoes J.P., Schoiswohl, S., Schlee, W., Basso, L., Bernal-Robledano, A., Boecking, B., Cima, R., Denys, S., Engelke, M., Escalera-Balsera, A., Gallego-Martinez, A., Gallus, S., Kikidis, D., López-Escámez, J.A., Marcrum, S.C., Markatos, N., Martin-Lagos, J., Martinez-Martinez, M., Mazurek, B., Vassou, E., Jarach, C.M., Mueller-Locatelli, N., Neff, P., Niemann, U., Kader Omar, H., Puga, C., Schleicher, M., Unnikrishnan, V., Perez-Carpena, P., Pryss, R., Robles-Bolivar, P., Rose, M., Schecklmann, M., Schiele, T., Schobel, J., Spiliopoulou, M., Stark, S., Vogel, C., Wunder, N., Zachou, Z. & Langguth, B. (2023). The statistical analysis plan for the unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients randomized clinical trial (UNITI-RCT). <i>Trials</i> 24, 472 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-023-07303-2
	Mazurek, B., Schulze, H., Schlee, W., & Dobel, C. (2023). Tinnitus at the Junction of Traditional Medicine and Modern Technology. <i>Nutrients</i> , 15(8), 1898. https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15081898
	Schoiswohl, S., Langguth, B., Weber, F. C., Abdelnaim, M. A., Hebel, T., & Schecklmann, M. (2023). Activate & fire: a feasibility study in combining acoustic stimulation and continuous theta burst stimulation in chronic tinnitus. <i>BMC neurology</i> , 23(1), 14. https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-022-03036-y
	Engelke M, Simões J, Vogel C., Schoiswohl S, Schecklmann M, Wöflflick S, Pryss R, Probst Th, Langguth B, Schlee W (2023). Pilot study of a smartphone-based tinnitus therapy using structured counseling and sound therapy: A multiple-baseline design with ecological momentary assessment. <i>PLOS Digit Health</i> 2(1): e0000183. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000183
Only abstract available	Schoiswohl, S., Langguth, B., Weber, F. C., Abdelnaim, M. A., Hebel, T., Mack, W., & Schecklmann, M. (2022). One way or another: treatment effects of 1 Hz rTMS using different current directions in a small sample of tinnitus patients. <i>Neuroscience Letters</i> , 137026. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2022.137026
	Schlee W, Neff P, Simoes J, Lanquath B, Schoiswohl S, Steinberger H, Norman M, Spiliopoulou M, Schobel J,

Social Media

Key Facts

- Coordinator: Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg, AG eHealth
- Co-Coordinator: Stefan Schoiswohl, University Clinic Regensburg, AG eHealth
- Project Network Manager: Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg, Center for Neuromodulation
- 13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers
- Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date
- Large European Network of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- Goal: Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- CORDIS database

Upcoming Events

No events found

Figure 6. Screenshot of the scientific publications at the UNITI website